

FRAMEWORK-DRIVEN GUIDELINE GENERATION FOR AI ADOPTION: A RISK-BASED PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

The adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) presents unique risks that existing frameworks inadequately address, including issues of accountability, accuracy, fairness, safety, and privacy. According to AI Incident Database, there is an increase of 156% of published AI incidents from the year 2020 to 2024. This study bridges the gap between reported AI incidents and actionable countermeasures by analyzing an AI incident repository and contextualizing risks with mitigative strategies drawn from the literature. A knowledge graph was developed to integrate contextual data, risks, and countermeasures, enabling the generation of customizable, risk-based guidelines tailored to specific applications and stakeholders. Key findings include the identification of countermeasures for diverse AI risks, emphasizing the need for systematic risk assessment throughout the AI life cycle. The developed prototype serves as both a risk assessment tool and risk reference database in an enhanced enterprise risk management framework which facilitates responsible AI adoption, guiding developers, risk managers, and policymakers in advancing ethical and sustainable AI practices. This work lays the groundwork for automated tools that enhance scalability and usability in addressing AI risks in various organizational contexts.

Keywords: *Responsible AI; Risk; Countermeasure; Framework; Guideline*

1. INTRODUCTION

The growing reliance on artificial intelligence (AI) technologies introduces unique risks that are not fully addressed by existing risk management frameworks [1] [2]. Unlike traditional systems, the nondeterministic nature of AI outputs creates challenges in evaluating their reliability, fairness, and safety [3]. Current research highlights various approaches to responsible AI, including the European Union's AI Act, which categorizes risks into unacceptable, high, limited, and minimal levels [4] [5], alongside other guidelines provided by organizations such as the World Economic Forum [6] and ISO [7]. However, these efforts primarily focus on high-level principles and compliance requirements, leaving a significant gap in providing actionable, context-specific countermeasures for managing AI risks effectively. This is reiterated in a study that mapped the provisions in NIST NSF 2.0, COBIT 2019, ISO 27001:2022 and ISO 42001:2023 to risks of Large Language Model (LLM) which

indicated significant gaps in risk management [8]. More recently, LLM is leveraged in autonomous decision-making in various forms of agentic workflow [9]. In this regard, AI agents are equipped to learn, reason, and update their knowledge bases dynamically. In fact, AI agents will manage production lines, optimize supply-chain operations with minimum human supervision and handle customer support and fraud detection by the year 2028, where 33% of enterprise software applications are expected to include agentic AI [10]. However, existing frameworks struggle to model the unpredictable actions of autonomous agents arising from their independent decision-making [11, 12].

Although incident repositories such as the AI Incident Database (AIID) [13] and the OECD AI Incidents Monitor [14] provide valuable documentation of real-world AI harms, they fail to offer targeted recommendations or frameworks for mitigating these issues in practice. Moreover, the published AI incidents has increased from 109 in 2020 to 279 in 2024 which represents an increased

of 156% in the period. This prompted prior studies on AI governance to introduce conceptual frameworks, such as the AI TRiSM [15] and SOTEC models [16]. However, these frameworks lack systematic methods for integrating real-world data to inform lifecycle-based risk assessments. Similarly, ethical risk management frameworks, such as the enhanced Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) model, address broad organizational risks but do not comprehensively incorporate AI-specific technological and analytical risks [17]. In fact, the study asserted that when ethical risks were identified, no solutions were at hand which led to the formation of an enhanced ERM framework in accordance with Figure 1. To bridge these gaps, this study introduces a framework-driven approach to generating customized, risk-based guidelines for AI adoption that supports the formation of a risk assessment tool and risk reference database as envisaged in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Enhanced ERM Framework [17]

Based on published standards [3, 7, 18] and guidelines [6, 19, 20], a proposed risk-based guideline should consider the dimensions of risk management processes, phases in the AI life cycle, and stakeholders that are responsible for the required activities. The three-dimensional approach is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Three-Dimensional Consideration for a Risk-Based Guideline

[17] analyzed 277 responses from 229 businesses to identify gaps in enterprise risk management (ERM) practices and proposed an enhanced ERM framework focused on ethical risks. On the other hand, [16] categorized risks in autonomous and intelligent systems (AIS) in the automotive and healthcare domains using the SOTEC framework (structure, organizational, technological, epidemiological and cultural), but did not address the need to evaluate risks throughout the AI life cycle.

[15] proposed the Artificial Intelligence Trust, Risk, and Security Management (AI TRiSM) framework, highlighting challenges and potential improvements, including adversarial attacks and related threats. Although it emphasized adaptability and scalability for evolving AI technologies, it lacked specific references to stakeholder roles. [21] identified metrics to measure sustainability, accuracy, fairness, and explainability—key factors opposing AI risks, and provided tests for the AI life cycle. However, it did not identify stakeholders as risk owners or assign responsibility for countermeasures. [22] presented computational methods for risk analysis with examples for Automated Driving Systems (ADS).

Table 1 summarizes the composition of these related studies in terms of these dimensions. Each study contributed to risk management processes within an AI context, with the "in context" criterion assessing whether its approaches were validated using real incidents, field settings, or specific AI models. With the exception of [17] which focused on non-technical risks, none of the listed studies in Table 1 fully account for the three-dimensional aspects of the risk management process, AI life cycle, and stakeholders.

Table 1:

Comparative summary of related studies

Ref.	Dimensional Consideration			
	Risk Management Process	AI Life Cycle	Stakeholder (Risk Owner)	Applied the proposed solution in context
[15]	√	√	X	√
[16]	√	X	√	√
[17]	√	√	√	√
[21]	√	√	X	√
[22]	√	X	X	√

This research aims to develop a structured framework that enables organizational

procurement teams to systematically identify risks and determine effective mitigation strategies during the implementation of AI systems. This study aligns risk management activities with the AI life cycle phases, ensuring continuous monitoring and evaluation. Additionally, it seeks to establish clear role delineation and accountability among internal and external stakeholders—such as data, tools, model, and infrastructure providers—to enhance the reliability and governance of AI deployment. Hence, this study aims to address the following research questions:

1. How can actionable countermeasures for AI-related risks be identified through the analysis of real-world incidents?
2. How can the generation of risk-based guidelines be facilitated in a manner that is dependent upon the selected context, identified risks, and corresponding countermeasures?
3. How can the integration of the AI life cycle and stakeholder responsibilities be ensured within the development of these guidelines?

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, the AIAAIC repository was used due its ease of downloading as well as the availability of crucial information related to the sector and technology. In total, there were twelve steps involved in this study which can be divided into three categories, as illustrated in Figure 3. As of 24 June 2024, the downloaded repository contained 1,534 rows with 16 fields or columns.

Figure 3: Research procedure

A. Data Preparation

The AI incident repository, sourced from the AIAAIC website (<https://www.aiaaic.org>), contained 16 fields detailing application contexts, associated risks, and other metadata. The

technology field served as a basis to examine the use cases and the associated issues reported. The dataset was prepared by extracting unique technology entries, splitting composite entries into discrete rows, and renaming the 'technology' field to 'application' for clarity. Multiple issues listed in a single column were similarly separated into individual entries, with the 'issue(s)' field renamed 'risk' to emphasize their relevance in risk management. Table 2 presents a sample record from the AIAAIC repository. The record illustrates the structure and content of an AI-related incident in the online database prior to any data processing implemented in this study.

Table 2: A Sample Record from AIAAIC Repository

AIAAIC ID	AIAAIC1539
Headline	Dream Machine AI video generator makes porn
Type	Issue
Released	2024
Occured	2024
Country(ies)	USA
Sector(s)	Media / entertainment / sports / art
Deployer(s)	-
Developer(s)	Luma Labs
System name(s)	Dream Machine
Technology(ies)	Text-to-video
Purpose(s)	Generate video
Media trigger(s)	User comments/complaints
Issue(s)	Privacy; Safety
Transparency	Governance
Description/links	https://www.aiaaic.org/aiaaic-repository/ai-algorithmic-and-automation-incidents/dream-machine-ai-video-generator-makes-porn

Table 3 illustrates the format of the table in the end of the data preparation exercise. Multiple records may be produced after this exercise for each original record as the distinct application and risk are separated.

Table 3: A sample record after data preparation

application	Text-to-video
purpose	Generate video
sector	Media / entertainment / sports / art
risk name	Privacy
risk phase	{human annotated}
ctms_name	{curated from literature}
ctms_phase	{human annotated}
stakeholder	{human annotated}

B. Data Population

As discussed in Section I, this study focused on two specific groups of risks. Thus, issues related to competition, collusion, malicious use of AI, surveillance for national interests, employment, human rights, and environmental hazards were excluded. Terms in the "issue" field, such as "accuracy," "reliability," and "appropriateness," were converted to risk-related terms like "inaccuracy," "unreliability," and "requirements gap." Entries lacking descriptive URLs as detailed references were also excluded.

A 'countermeasure' is defined as a targeted method to address specific risks associated with AI applications. For each risk-application pair, countermeasures were identified using systematic literature searches on platforms like Google Scholar, with a focus on studies cited in at least five peer-reviewed sources to ensure validity. Keywords were adapted as needed to capture related concepts. The resulting countermeasures were mapped to phases in the AI lifecycle and categorized by responsible stakeholders, ensuring a structured and actionable dataset. For example, for the application "Automatic License Plate Recognition" (ALPR) and the risk "inaccuracy," searches included terms like "ALPR and inaccuracy," and if no results were found, "ALPR and accuracy" or "ALPR and accurate" were used. The research tool *Publish or Perish* facilitated this search [23].

To ensure practicality and potential adoption, the selected countermeasure had to be cited in at least five other studies. Once a suitable countermeasure was identified, the search was stopped, and an additional reference citing it was included for verification. Table 3 serves as a practical blueprint for constructing a knowledge graph that maps complex relationships between AI risks and countermeasures. It also bridges the gap between theoretical frameworks and their application in real-world scenarios. Referring to Table 4, the attributes were translated into label of nodes while the fields were used to form properties in the associated nodes in the knowledge graph.

Table 4: The information required for the knowledge graph

Attribute	Field
Context	Application, Purpose, and Sector
Risk	Name, Phase
Countermeasure	Name, Phase
Stakeholder	Name

To account for the many-to-many relationships between the entities required in this

study, a graph-based method was chosen due to its effectiveness [19]. Hence, a knowledge graph was created using the Neo4j Desktop and Python programming language using VSCode as code editor. The source code is available as a reference for interested readers at the website: <https://www.github.com/renaissance2005/fd-guidelines>.

C. Framework Application

The framework integrated a knowledge graph with a local Large Language Model (LLM) to generate dynamic, context-specific guidelines. Users interact with the system through a series of selections: (1) defining the application context, (2) identifying relevant risks, and (3) choosing countermeasures for each risk. The knowledge graph dynamically retrieves data at each step, guiding user inputs and informing the LLM. The system outputs guidelines tailored to the user's specified parameters, enhancing the framework's practicality for diverse organizational needs. The LLM used was the Llama 3.1:8b variant, running via the Ollama platform [24]. Llama 3.1 was chosen for its open-source nature and ability to run locally, which ensures data privacy and avoids the latency and cost of external APIs. In fact, a study showed that it performed better than GPT-3.5, a proprietary model [25]. While GPT-4 or Claude 2 offer advanced capabilities, they require cloud access and entail usage fees, making them less practical for this implementation. At the time of this study, Llama 3.1 was the latest open-source LLM released by Meta AI and available for download from Hugging Face website (<http://www.huggingface.co>). Ollama provided a user-friendly interface to run the local LLM with minimal configuration.

The choice to use a local LLM and database ensured confidentiality and avoided rate-limit issues common with proprietary LLMs. Figure 4 illustrates the system setup to generate risk-based guidelines. The system allowed users to make selections from information retrieved from the knowledge graph, which was then passed to the local LLM to generate coherent guideline sentences.

To use the system, the user selected the application context, followed by the risks to consider. They then chose countermeasures for each selected risk. Based on these inputs, the system generated guidelines by combining context, risks, and countermeasures. Information from the knowledge graph was retrieved at each

step to support the user's selections and guide the guideline-generation process.

Figure 4: Generation of framework-driven guideline

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From 1,534 list of issues recorded in the repository, there were 88 distinct lists of technology entries extracted, of which 38 unique entries were curated and renamed as application. Additionally, the entries with countermeasure obtained from extant literature are listed in Appendix 1. This table is a critical resource for practitioners, offering actionable solutions for common AI risks across diverse applications, such as chatbots, autonomous systems, and surveillance technologies. Due to conceptual fuzziness in AI, there were different combinations of keyword applied on the full text of the article to search for the relevant countermeasure [26].

Consequently, the data were entered into an excel file which was used to generate the knowledge graph. The excel file and Python code used to build the system are given in the same preceding URL. In a nutshell, the system developed was divided into 4 tabs, with the first three tabs involve selections by the user while the final tab generated the guidelines based on prior selections. Figure 5 depicts the sample view from the 4 tabs as executed.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 5: The AI Acquisition Guidelines Generator with (a) Context (b) Risk (c) Countermeasure (d) Guidelines

As highlighted in Table 1, none of the previous studies considered all three dimensions of the risk management process, the AI life cycle, and stakeholder participation. In addition, the risks analyzed in this study were derived from real-world incidents reported in an online repository. Furthermore, the applicable risks and countermeasures are context-dependent, as the options are displayed to users based on the selected context, thereby minimizing human error and guiding attention toward the relevant risks and controls.

Comparatively, this study advanced the work of previous studies in the following manner:

- i. **Advancements over Ethical Risk Frameworks [17, 20]:** This study not only highlighted ethical risks but also provided actionable countermeasures and stakeholder-specific guidance, addressing the operational gap in [17] and [20].
- ii. **Life-cycle Integration [15, 16]:** While [15] and [16] provided theoretical risk management frameworks, this study incorporated life-cycle considerations which facilitates monitoring and assessment of required activities.
- iii. **Stakeholder-specific Roles [15, 21]:** This study surpasses [15] and [21] by clearly defining stakeholder responsibilities, a critical component for operationalizing AI governance that is often overlooked in existing models.
- iv. **Use of Real-world Data [15, 22]:** Unlike [15] and [22], which primarily rely on conceptual models, this study integrates real-world data from the AIAAIC repository, underscoring its practical benefits.

4. LIMITATIONS AND WAY FORWARD

Admittedly, an empirical comparison with other frameworks was not available at the time of this study, as it would require the practical application of all stated frameworks in a real-world environment. Additionally, this study only considered the various academic databases available for the author's institution which include ArXiv, Scopus, Web of Science, IEEE Explore and ScienceDirect. In addition, the search for risk

controls and countermeasures were not exhaustive as it was not the intention of this study to produce a catalog of mitigation strategies for all available risks.

Future enhancement may explore automated scrapping of published incidents and risks as well as extractions of abstracts from academic papers regarding the risk mitigation strategies and controls proposed. Additionally, LLM can be used to derive the associated stages in the life cycle as well as stakeholders without the requirement for human annotation.

5. CONCLUSION

In a nutshell, this study made the following contributions to the field of responsible AI:

1. **Context-specific Countermeasures:** By linking AI incidents to specific risks and identifying actionable countermeasures, the research addresses the lack of operational solutions in existing guidelines.
2. **Lifecycle-based Risk Assessment:** The proposed framework accounts for risks and mitigation strategies throughout the entire AI life cycle, ensuring a holistic approach to responsible AI governance.
3. **Stakeholder Integration:** Unlike previous frameworks, this study explicitly identifies stakeholders responsible for implementing countermeasures, ensuring accountability and operational clarity.
4. **Practical Applicability:** The system integrates a local LLM for generating customized guidelines, providing a scalable and adaptable tool for organizations to manage AI risks effectively.

By using this framework, procurement team, risk managers, project managers, internal developers and maintenance team will be able to set the required expectations regarding the risk pertaining to the use of AI in the organizations. By addressing both ethical and technological risks, the proposed framework extends beyond the scope of existing frameworks and guidelines, contributing to the development of adaptive and actionable solutions for responsible AI adoption.

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Appendix 1: The countermeasure for the selected application and risk

Application	Risk	Countermeasure	Keyword (full text)	Reference
ALPR/ANPR	Inaccuracy	Robust local feature points	ANPR & accuracy	[27, 28]
	Unreliability	Integrating data from an alternate source	ANPR	[28, 29]
	Privacy	Store data in shortest amount of time	traffic & duration of storage	[30, 31]
Behavioural analysis/ monitoring	Bias	Conduct regular fairness audit	bias & monitoring	[32, 33]
Blood measurement algorithm	Inaccuracy	Anti-Motion Interference Wearable Device	blood oxygen & accuracy	[34, 35]
	Unreliability	Apply digital filtering method	blood oxygen & reliability	[34, 36]
	Appropriateness	Conduct requirements engineering	requirements & artificial intelligence	[37, 38]
Bot/ Agent	Safety	Implement guardrails	chatbot & safety	[39, 40]
CCTV/ Surveillance System	Inaccuracy	Employ feature importance	Surveillance & Accuracy	[27, 28]
	Unreliability	Use MPEG4 over wavelet	CCTV & reliability	[41, 42]
	Bias	Domain-conditional model with explicit combination of per-domain class predictions	visual & bias	[43, 44]
	Security	Implement access control	CCTV & security	[45, 46]
	Privacy	Use multiparty key-sharing scheme for access control	surveillance system & privacy	[46, 47]
Chatbot	Inaccuracy	Correction with external evidence	chatbot & accuracy	[39, 48]
	Unreliability	Multi-agent interaction	chatbot & reliability	[39, 49]
	Requirement gap	Conduct requirements engineering	requirements & artificial intelligence	[37, 38]
	Bias	replacing biased texts in the data set with neutral texts	chatbot & bias	[39, 50]
	Plagiarism	Use the cross-language plagiarism detection mechanism	plagiarism & detection	[51, 52]
	Copyright infringement	Watermarking	copyright & generative AI	[53, 54]
	Disinformation/ misinformation	Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback	chatbot & misinformation	[39, 55]
	Privacy	Use differential privacy	privacy & artificial intelligence	[56, 57]
	Safety	Implement guardrails	chatbot & safety	[39, 40]
Self-driving system/ Driver assistance system	Inaccuracy	Use YOLOv7 architecture for realtime object detection	autonomous driving & performance	[58, 59]
	Unreliability	Detection mechanism for sensor fault	autonomous driving	[60, 61]
	Safety	Use the YOLOv7 architecture for real-time object detection	autonomous driving	[58, 59]
Computer Vision	Inaccuracy	Combine technical and aesthetic scores	computer vision & accuracy	[62, 63]

Application	Risk	Countermeasure	Keyword (full text)	Reference
	Unreliability	Semantically construct aesthetic features for Image Aesthetics Assessment (IAA)	computer vision & reliability	[64, 65]
	Bias	Semantically construct aesthetic features for image aesthetics assessment (IAA)	computer vision & bias	[64, 65]
	Requirement gap	Perform requirements engineering	requirements & artificial intelligence	[37, 38]
Facial recognition	Inaccuracy	Use facial quality assessment	facial recognition & accuracy	[66, 67]
	Privacy	Use homomorphic encryption	facial recognition & privacy	[68, 69]
Gaze redirection system	Requirement gap	Perform requirements engineering	requirements & artificial intelligence	[37, 38]
Dataset	Bias	Oversample minority class	class imbalance	[70, 71]
	Privacy	Use encryption for medical records	privacy & medical records	[72, 73]
Robotics	Privacy	Detecting exposure by conducting network scans	robotics & privacy	[74, 75]
	Security	Activate security features in the transport and application layers	robotics & security	[74, 75]
	Safety	Incorporate human-in-the-loop	robotics & safety	[76, 77]
Deepfake-audio	Copyright infringement	Watermarking	copyright & generative AI	[53, 54]
Deepfake-video	Disinformation/misinformation	Use a hybrid of signature- and anomaly-based detection mechanism	deepfakes & detection	[55, 78]
Drone	Unauthorized attack	Use the Received Signal Strength Indication (RSSI) technique and the trilateration method	drone & unauthorized	[79, 80]
Emotion recognition	Inaccuracy	Use multimodal deep learning approach	video & identification	[81, 82]
	Bias	Use Reducing Bias Amplification (RBA)	visual & bias	[43, 83]
Iris scanning	Privacy	Apply iris template protection	iris & privacy	[84, 85]
Prediction Algorithm/ Predictive Statistical Analysis	Inaccuracy	Use high-resolution vital signs time series and electronic medical record to train the model	prediction & model	[86, 87]
Pricing Algorithm	Bias	Use discrimination-free pricing formula	pricing & discrimination	[88, 89]
Recommendation algorithm	Bias	Use a reweighting mechanism as bias-mitigating module	bias & detection system	[44, 90]
	Safety	Implement measurement criteria	recommendation & safety	[91, 92]
Text analysis	Privacy	Use encryption for medical records	privacy & medical record	[72, 73]
	Bias	Use preferential sampling	discrimination & models	[93, 94]

Application	Risk	Countermeasure	Keyword (full text)	Reference
Text-to-image/ Image generator	Copyright infringement	Watermarking	copyright & generative AI	[53, 54]
Text-to-image	Bias	Combine the diffusion model and the high-efficiency transformer model for text-to-image synthesis	visual & bias	[95, 96]
Text-to-speech/ Voice generator	Copyright infringement	Watermarking	copyright & generative AI	[53, 54]
Virtual reality	Safety	Use authentication protocol for device-to-device sharing	virtual & safety	[57, 97]
Voice recognition	Copyright infringement	Watermarking	copyright & generative AI	[53, 54]